

INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATION FOR STANDARDIZATION (ISO) IMPLEMENTATION IN SCHOOLS DIVISION OF BATANGAS PROVINCE: BASIS FOR SUSTAINABLE QUALITY MANAGEMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study was to determine the description of the implementation of the ISO in the division in terms of organizational context; leadership and commitment; support and resources; performance evaluation; and continual improvement as well as the problems and issues encountered in ISO implementation. The descriptive method of research was used in the study applying survey technique. The questionnaire was the main data gathering instrument complemented with unstructured interview with sixty (60) respondents out of two hundred forty-seven (247) total personnel, randomly selected. The findings of the study were: (1.) the ISO implementation is efficiently delivered relative to its organizational context, leadership and commitment, support and resources, performance evaluation, and continual improvement; (2.) the teamwork and collaboration, feedback mechanism, and risk-based management need to be enhanced are the most pressing issues and challenges encountered in ISO implementation; (3.) the proposed Sustainability Management Program is Kapeng Barako's House of Quality. The research was holistic and with original value.

Keywords: Organizational Context, Quality Management System, Support and Resources, Performance Evaluation, Continual Improvement, Philippines.